

THE EFFECT OF CYCLIC WATER ABSORPTION ON THE ILSS OF CF/BMI COMPOSITES

Luo Yunfeng, Duan Yuexin, Sun Yongchun, Zhao Yan, Du Shanyi
School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University
No.37, Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, 100191, China

Keywords: *carbon fiber, BMI composites, cyclic water absorption, interlaminar shear strength, hygrothermal*

Abstract

In order to quantify the changes of interfacial properties in CF/BMI composites at cyclical hygrothermal environment, the moisture weight and ILSS of CF/BMI composites specimen of each stage during three absorption-desorption cyclical stages was tested. The results showed the ILSS of composites after water absorption dramatically decreased, but it could make a comeback on the whole after removal of water.

1 introduction

Polymer matrix carbon fiber composites are widely used in aerospace, automotive and civil industries due to their attractive properties, for example, high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent corrosion resistance and impact resistance. Despite the desirable properties of polymer matrix composites, one major disadvantage of them is their tendency to absorb water in humid environments. The absorbed moisture has many detrimental effects on the composite performance.

Moisture diffusion behaviour for FRP is investigated by Springer et al. [1]. In this research, moisture content was quantified by measuring weight of FRPs, and the moisture concentration in the

material was determined by means of Fick's law. The distribution of moisture content generates stress in composite materials.

As aircraft materials, Polymer-based composite materials are often exposed to complicated hygrothermal environments, where water molecules can easily migrate into the polymeric matrix and reach at the interface between fiber and matrix resin. Interfacial properties can be investigated by several means: macromechanical tests such as inter/intra laminar shear stress measurements; and micromechanical tests such as the single fiber pull-out (SFPO), single fiber fragmentation test (SFFT), and microdroplet tests [2].

As a macro-mechanical test method, the ILSS can be used to characterise the interfacial bond between fiber and matrix. The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of cyclic water absorption on the interfacial properties of composites using interlaminar shear strength test.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material and Sample preparation

The BMI resin QY8911 used in this study was supplied by Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute. Polyacrylonitrile

based carbon fibers (CCF300) were produced by Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd.

All composite panels were manufactured by autoclave molding according to curing process specified by resin manufacturers.

2.2 Cyclic absorption and desorption

Prior to absorption experiments, the specimens were dried in a vacuum oven at about 70°C until the weight stabilized. The specimens were then immersed in distilled water at 71°C for 14 days until moisture saturated proximately. Periodically, the specimens were removed from the water bath, wiped dry with tissue paper and weighed using an Adventure OHAUS analytical balance with a resolution of 0.1mg. After measuring the weight specimens were immediately immersed into the distilled water. After moisture absorption for 14 days specimens were removed from water and dried in a desiccator at 85°C until a constant weight was obtained. During the dryness the weight of specimens were measured periodically. The same specimen was then used in the second and third absorption. In the re-absorption steps, the percentage weight gain was determined using the original dry weight as reference. The same absorption-desorption cycle was then performed three times. The weight values obtained from five specimens were averaged.

The percent moisture content M defined as

$$M = \frac{W - W_d}{W_d} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where W is the weight of moist material and W_d is the weight of dry

material.

2.3 Interlaminar Shear Strength Test

In the cyclic absorption-desorption experiments, the Short Beam Shear samples of 20×6×2mm³ were immersed in distilled water at 71°C for 7 days and 14 days respectively, then were removed from water and dried in a desiccator at 85°C until a constant weight was obtained. The same specimen was then used in the second and third absorption. The ILSS of composite samples suffered from different conditioning procedures was performed on Instron 5500 testing machine at 25°C and 150°C respectively. On an average five specimens were tested and mean value of shear strength was calculated.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 Cyclic moisture absorption and desorption behavior

The three cycles of moisture absorption of CFRP panel as a function of time were shown in Fig.1: the second and third absorption steps exhibit consistently higher diffusivity and uptake than the first absorption. This implies that during first absorption the network structure has changed and the more microvoids and microcracks formed may induce more open and more accessible to additional water in the subsequent re-absorption steps. The cyclical moisture absorption behaviour of CCF300/QY8911 composite is similar to the previous work about the cyclical moisture absorption of pure rein reported by Apicella [3-5] and Wong et al. [6-9]. After the polymer has been exposed to the absorbent during the first absorption step, the subsequent re-absorption steps often exhibit higher diffusivity and higher saturation level. Some authors have

linked this behaviour to the irreversible damage induced by absorbed moisture [3-5]. Another opinion is that the higher absorption level in the re-absorption is associated with the structural relaxation of polymers, because of the plasticization effect of the penetrant [6-9], but these explanations are difficult to establish experimentally.

Fig.1 Moisture absorption curve

Fig.2 Moisture desorption curve

The three cycles of moisture desorption of CFRP panel as a function of time were shown in Fig.2: the third desorption step exhibiting more rapid desorption rate than the first and second desorption, that validates indirectly more accessible microvoids or microcracks formed in the subsequent re-absorption steps.

3.2 Interlaminar shear strength of the moisture absorption-desorption cycles

The mechanical performances of composites after absorbing moisture are degraded. The ILSS of immersing for 7 days and 14 days after suffering different moisture absorption-desorption cycles is plotted in Fig.3 and Fig.4 respectively. The results reveal that the ILSS After immersing for 7 days, regardless how experienced absorption-desorption cycles, decreased about 9% at 25 °C and decreased about 38% at 150°C. Otherwise, the ILSS After immersing for 14 days, regardless how experienced absorption-desorption cycles, decreased about 9% at 25°C and decreased about 42% at 150°C. However, the composites after first cycle perform a little higher ILSS than those after suffering more cycles, regardless of the temperature, as shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Moreover, the ILSS of composites at original dry state decreased about 26% under high temperature, and the ILSS of composites after immersion of 7 days just decreased about 8% under room temperature, with the comparison of 50% under high temperature. Therefore, it can be concluded that high temperature and high moisture has great effect on the properties of composites.三

Fig.3 The ILSS of immersing for 7 days after suffering different moisture

absorption-desorption cycles

(Note: In fig3. a—original dry state、b—immersed for 7 days、c1-c2—immersed for 7 days after the first to second cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 7 days、c1-c2—immersed for 7 days after the first to second cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 14 days)

Fig.4 The ILSS of immersing for 14 days after suffering different moisture absorption-desorption cycles

(Note: In fig4. a—original dry state、b—immersed for 14 days、c1-c2—immersed for 14 days after the first to second cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 7 days、c1-c2—immersed for 14 days after the first to second cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 14 days)

After composites samples suffered different period of absorption-desorption cycles, the ILSS properties were shown in Fig.5. The ILSS of composites after desorption roughly restore to the original dry state at room temperature and restore above 80% at 150°C, but the ILSS during second and third desorption steps are slightly lower than one during first desorption, it can be explained that there were more damages such as microvoids and microcracks had formed after first absorption-desorption cycle and this result can be supported by the water absorption curves.

As revealed in Fig.3, 4 and 5, the

ILSS of composites is determined by the last absorption-desorption step, and is unrelated to the processes in between. This indirectly suggests that the role of water inside composites is mainly physical, not chemical.

Fig.5 The ILSS of drying at 85°C after suffering different moisture absorption-desorption cycles

(Note: In fig5. a—original dry state、b1-b3—the first to third cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 7 days、c1-c3—the first to third cycle of drying at 85°C after immersing for 14 days)

4 Conclusions

The water absorption saturation can reach after composites were immersed in water at 71°C for 14 days in this research work. Then during the absorption-desorption cycles the re-absorption steps exhibit higher diffusivity and higher uptake. In addition, the ILSS of composites changed so much according to the temperature and reduced dramatically if high temperature combining with high humidity, however, the humidity has less affection on composites ILSS at room temperature. At last, the ILSS of composites at room temperature roughly restore to the original dry state after desorption and restore above 80% at 150°C, when it was

exposed in water at 71 °C for a short period.

References

- [1] Chi-Hung, G.S.Springer “Moisture absorption and desorption of composite materials”. J Compos Mater 1976; 10:2-21
- [2] J. P. Favre. “Review of test methods and testing for assessment of fiber-matrix adhesion”. Proceedings of Conference, Interfacial Phenomena in Composite Materials 1989, Sheffield, pp7-12
- [3] A. Apicella, L. Nicolais. “Hygrothermal history dependence of equilibrium moisture sorption in epoxy resins”. Polymer 1981; 8:1064-1067
- [4] Giulio C. Sarti, Antonio Apicella. “Non-equilibrium glassy properties and their relevance in Case II transport kinetics”. Polymer 1980; 9:1031-1036
- [5] A. Apicella, L. Nicolais. “Effect of thermal history on water sorption, elastic properties and the glass transition of epoxy resins”. Polymer 1979; 9:1143-1148
- [6] T. C. Wong and L. J. Broutman (1985a), Polym. Eng. Sci., 25, 521
- [7] T. C. Wong and L. J. Broutman (1985b), Polym. Eng. Sci., 25, 529
- [8] R. W. Connelly, N. R. McCoy, H. B. Hopfenberg and M. E. Stewart (1987), J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 34,703
- [9] M. E. Stewart, H. B. Hopfenberg and N. R. McCoy (1987), J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 34,721